

Violin Wood Flames Angle Detection With Weighted Hough Algorithm.

Introduction

The objective of this project is to estimate the orientation of the wood flames on the back of a violin. Detecting and determining the angles of wood flames on a violin, even in an approximate manner, is a challenging task, primarily due to the wide variety of appearances that violins can exhibit (see figure 1). The flames can vary in shape, size, and intensity, which poses difficulties in accurately identifying and outlining them in all cases. Furthermore, the presence of other elements on the violin's back, such as scratches and textures, can further complicate the detection process. Therefore, it is crucial to develop an effective and robust algorithm to consistently detect wood flames.

To achieve this, we have chosen to employ a classic computer vision approach. Line detection is a well-established task in computer vision, and we have specifically chosen to use the Hough line detection algorithm, which we have modified into a **weighted** Hough algorithm to better suit the wood flame detection task.

In addition, we utilised previously trained deep learning models, namely the c-bout keypoint detection model and the "1 piece / 2 pieces" classification model, to assist us in this task. These models can aid in identifying the region of interest within the back of the violin.

Figure 1: Illustration of the variety of violin's back appearances.

This report will begin by providing a short explanation of the principles of Hough line detection. Then, we will describe the image preprocessing step, which plays a crucial role in the detection of wood flames. From there, we will explain the modified weighted Hough algorithm and the rationale behind its implementation. The report will then present the results obtained from the entire dataset. Finally, we will discuss potential ways to further improve the results.

Hough Line Detection

The technique used here to detect wood flames and, consequently, flame angles, is a modification of the “Hough line detection” algorithm. This is a well known classic computer vision technique to detect straight lines in an image, even if they are broken or incomplete. Detailed descriptions of this algorithm can be found [here](#) or [here](#). The technique used to detect wood flames, therefore flame angles, in this study is a modified version of the “Hough line detection” algorithm.

Figure 2: basic principle of Hough line detection with only 2 pixels. a) lines passing through the first pixel are given a score of 1. b) lines passing through the second pixel also get a score of 1. The lines that pass through the first and second pixel gets its score increased by 1.

The basic principle of the Hough line detection is shown figure 2. Imagine scattered dots on a blank image. Figure 2 represents such an image with only 2 dots. The objective is to identify the straight lines that pass through the *maximum number of dots*. One approach is to select a single dot and draw all possible lines that pass through it, rotating the line at different angle (see figure 2-a). Each drawn line is assigned a score of 1. This process is then repeated for every dot (see figure 2-b). If the *very same line* is present in multiple dots, the score gets *incremented* by 1 each time it appears. In figure 2-b, the line connecting the two dots has a score of 2, while the other lines have a score of 1. By applying this technique to all dots, and selecting the lines with the highest scores, we can identify the prominent lines in an image.

The real Hough line algorithm is slightly more complex than this simplified explanation. Indeed, it requires a transformation of pixels from the image space into the line-parameters space using polar coordinates. However, the fundamental principle remains consistent with what has been presented. For more detailed information, please refer to the provided links.

Image Preprocessing

A carefully designed image preprocessing is crucial in order to apply the Hough line detection algorithm. Indeed, the image needs to be transformed into a *binary skeletonized image*. In a binary image, pixel values are either 0 or 1, with 0 representing the background and 1 representing the *pixels of interest*, i.e. the dots in figure 2. For our specific case, an ideal binary skeletonized image of a violin's back would have everything except the wood flames set to 0, and the flames themselves represented by a 1-pixel line. The whole preprocessing pipeline is illustrated in figure 3. The violin in figure 3 is considered “easy”, with a lot of well defined flames.

The first step in detecting the flames is to define a region of interest within the violin's back. This is done by utilising the c-bout keypoints (the green circles in figure 2-a) that were previously predicted by our keypoint detection model. By using these keypoints, we are able to rotate the violin and define a rectangle within its back.

Figure 3: image preprocessing pipeline for Hough line detection. The green circles represent the c-bout keypoints, which are used to define the region of interest.

Once the region of interest is isolated, the image is converted to grayscale and its contrast is enhanced using the CLAHE algorithm (see figure 2-b). This process not only highlights the flames but also serves as image normalisation.

The next step involves applying an edge detection filter. A commonly used filter for this purpose is the Sobel filter, which is effective in highlighting areas where pixel values change rapidly. Additionally, the filter can be oriented to remove vertical lines, which are often overlaid on wood flames, as shown in Figure 3-c.

The output of the Sobel filter is often grainy and contains fine details. This "noisy" output can interfere with the functioning of the Hough line detection algorithm by introducing unwanted pixels in the skeletonized image. To address this, an additional preprocessing step is added to smooth out the fine texture. The image is first blurred to a certain degree, and then a threshold is applied to obtain a binary image like in figure 3-d.

Lastly, the skeletonized binary image is obtained by applying a Gabor filter with specific values. The flames, which were outlined by the previous preprocessing steps, now appear as one-pixel lines. This enables the image to be processed by the Hough line detection algorithm.

Figure 4: lines detected by the Hough line algorithm (highlighted in red) on the skeletonized image from figure 3. The mean angle of these lines is 0.4° , with 0° representing a horizontal line. The standard deviation of the angles is 1°

Based on our previous deep learning model, we can determine whether the violin is in one or two pieces. If it is in two pieces, we can easily run the Hough line algorithm on the left and right pieces separately.

The Hough line algorithm identifies the straight lines with the highest number of votes (see figure 4). To eliminate lines that are too similar, a non-maximum suppression (NMS) algorithm is applied. Additionally, a score threshold is used to retain only the lines that have more than half the votes of the line with the maximum number of votes. The resulting lines provide us with an average angle, a median angle, and an angle standard deviation.

On a violin that is considered "easy" like the one shown in Figure 3 and 4, the standard deviation of the angles generally ranges from 1° to 5° . However, on a more challenging violin, this standard deviation can be much larger. **Empirically, we have found that the angle standard deviation can be interpreted as an error probability.** A larger standard deviation indicates a higher likelihood of having an incorrect result.

Based on the standard deviation numbers, we estimate that this preprocessing, along with the standard Hough line algorithm, yields approximately 80% correct results on the entire dataset, which consists of around 43,000 images and 71,000 individual back pieces. To further enhance these results, we have developed a modified version of the Hough line algorithm.

Weighted Hough Line Detection

Before delving into the workings of the weighted Hough line, let's take a look at an example where the preprocessing, together with the standard Hough line algorithm, doesn't perform well. Figure 5 illustrates such a violin.

Figure 5: Line detection on a challenging violin. Highlighted in green is a patch of wood where the flames are not visible. The preprocessing filters captured random texture and scratches, leading to numerous unwanted detected lines and a significantly large angle standard deviation.

This violin back has some visible flames, but on a large patch of the cropped image, no flames are visible, as shown in the green area in figure 5. Due to the nature of the filters used in preprocessing, random scratches and texture are captured and results in a lots of little lines in the skeletonized image, while the flames are correctly captured as long continuous lines. Although the Hough algorithm successfully detects the flames, the presence of the small lines results in the detection of numerous incorrect lines. Consequently, this leads to a significantly large standard deviation (in this case 29°). Here the mean angle happens to be somewhat accurate by chance. However, it is important to note that in most cases, a standard deviation exceeding 15° indicates an incorrect mean angle prediction.

To address this challenge, we implemented the following technique. In the initial step, we assign *weights* to pixels in the skeletonized image based on the length of the line they belong to. For instance, if a line consists of 10 *connected* pixels, we assign a value of $\sqrt{10}$ to every pixel of that line. The square root is here to reduce the difference between long and small lines. We give

weights to the pixels by utilising a connected component algorithm. We obtain a skeletonized image with weighted pixels like in figure 6-a.

Figure 6: a) the skeletonized image from figure 5 with pixels weighted based on the length of the line they belong to. b) Pixel with small values are removed, c) modified weighted Hough line detection is applied, only the prominent lines are detected. This whole process results in a much more accurate angle prediction, with a standard deviation of only 1°.

With an image like this, it is easy to retain only the most prominent lines. This can be achieved by calculating the median value of all non-zero pixels, and by setting all pixels below this value to zero. This step effectively eliminates a significant amount of unwanted noise, as demonstrated in Figure 6-b.

This technique alone can greatly enhance the results, but we took it a step further by introducing the weighted Hough line algorithm. The concept is simple: in the standard Hough line algorithm, a line receives one vote for each pixel it passes through. In the weighted Hough line algorithm, *the vote is weighted by the value of the pixel*. As a result, only the prominent lines are detected, as shown in figure 6-c. This leads to much more precise results. For the particular violin of figure 5 and 6, the standard deviation went from 29° to 1°, as only correct flames were detected.

Sliding Window Hough Line

Even after applying the technique described earlier to filter out the smallest lines, another issue may still arise when there is a high density of somewhat horizontal flames, as in Figure 3. In some cases, we observed that lines are incorrectly detected *across* multiple flames, as they pass through numerous high-value pixels belonging to different flames. These incorrect lines typically have a relatively steep angle, as they need to pass through several flames.

To address this problem, a possibility is to limit the angular scope of the Hough line detection. For instance, we can restrict the detection to lines that deviate from the horizontal by less than 20°. However, this approach would prevent the detection of flames with steep angles. Although violins with steep-angled flames are rare, we aim for our algorithm to detect them specifically, as it is valuable to identify unusual violins.

In this paper, we propose an alternative approach to Hough line detection. Instead of restricting the angular range, we limit the spatial range by utilizing a sliding window technique. This principle is depicted in Figure 7. The Hough line algorithm is applied to a subsection of the image, which has the same width but a smaller height compared to the original image. In Figure 7, the subsection corresponds to one-third of the image height. The accumulator for this subsection is computed, and then the window slides down the image with a stride equal to half of the window's height. The accumulator for this new window is added to the previous accumulator. This

process is repeated until the window reaches the bottom of the image. The final accumulator is the sum of all accumulators and can be further processed using the non-max suppression algorithm, similar to the conventional Hough line algorithm.

Figure 7: Hough line detection using a sliding window with a height equal to one-third of the image's height. The Hough space accumulator of each window are summed to obtain an accumulator for the entire image.

Results

As previously mentioned, we found that the standard deviation of the detected angle serves as a reliable indicator of the accuracy of the angle prediction. To quantify this relationship, we manually reviewed the results for different standard deviation ranges. For each range, we randomly selected 200 images and determined the ratio of good predictions to bad predictions. This ratio was then considered as the error probability for that particular standard deviation range. From these results, we deduced a conversion law that relates the standard deviation to the error probability (see fig. 8-a).

By converting the standard deviation into error probability for the entire dataset, we can generate a visualisation of the error probability distribution (fig. 8-b). From this distribution, we observe that over 83% of all predictions have an error probability of less than 10%, and around 91% have an error probability of less than 20%. Overall, we can estimate that approximately 94% of all predictions are correct.

It is worth noting that around 75% of predictions with an error probability exceeding 60% are from violins that *do not have visible flames*, at least not within the cropped rectangle where the hough line detection is applied (see fig.3). Figure 9 showcases some examples of such violins.

Figure 8: a) correlation between the standard deviation of the detected angles and the error probability. b) distribution of error probabilities across the dataset.

Figure 9: 3 examples of violins where the algorithm failed to detect lines. On the first violin, the algorithm correctly detected flames on the left side, but failed to detect any flames on the right side. The second violin does not have any visible flames. The third violin, which has low resolution, exhibits very faint and dense flames that were not detected by the algorithm.

Conclusion and Prospects

Although the presented weighted Hough line detection algorithm is remarkably robust and effective with ~94% correct predictions, it does have certain limitations.

Firstly, the parameters used for image preprocessing aim to outline the flames and eliminate any other elements. Consequently, these parameters are a *compromise* between pixel gradient sensitivity and texture filtering. As a result, in certain cases, such as the third violin in figure 8, the flames are not accurately distinguished from the surrounding elements.

Secondly, due to the absence of direct confidence scores for line detection, there is no reliable approach to distinguish a violin without visible flames from a violin where the algorithm failed for other reasons. Furthermore, there are rare instances of violins with diverging flames, where the orientation of the flames at the top of the violin differs significantly from those at the bottom. In such cases, the algorithm will accurately detect the lines, but it will still yield a high standard deviation/error probability for the angle.

One potential solution to address these challenges would be to utilise the predictions of the Hough line detection algorithm with a minimal error probability to train a deep learning model. This model can be designed in a straightforward manner, incorporating a feature-extracting backbone, followed by a multi-layer perceptron, and concluding with a classification layer with a sigmoid activation function. The classification can be based on bins representing different angle ranges, spanning from -90° to $+90^\circ$, although the resolution of these bins is yet to be determined. However, there remains ongoing questions regarding this approach: if a model is trained on simpler examples (those with a low error probability), can it accurately predict outcomes for more challenging examples? Additionally, should we employ the raw output of the Hough line detection to train the model (multiple lines/angles), or solely rely on the mean or median angle? Nevertheless, this approach holds promise as a means to further enhance the results.